

C.R.M. AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS AS PREDICTORS OF CUSTOMER PREFERENCE OF ELECTRONIC BRANDS IN THE NIGER DELTA REGION

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ABSTRACT

The study examined two domain predictor variables and factors contained therein that are hypothesized to predict the preference of electronic brands by customers in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The survey method was adopted using questionnaire forms. Five cities of Asaba, Benin City, Yanagoo, Port-Harcourt and Calabar were selected for this study. From these cities, 92 retailers of electronic brands were randomly selected. A total of 1,110 questionnaire forms were deposited in dealers' showrooms across the towns and 778 were successfully retrieved. Data from the field were analyzed using regression tools and outcome suggest factors of customer retention, relationship management, privacy, family, peer group, technology, culture and competition to be significant influencers of brand preference tendencies among sampled customers. These two have a positive correlation coefficient with the dependent variable: brand preference. Three factors, however, were revealed to have a negative association with the dependent variable at a 5% level of significance. These include customer attraction, conversion and economics. Recommendations given are to the effect that brand managers should include these significant factors as they attempt to design customer-centric programmes. Again, the study warns of the risk of generalizing and extrapolating outcomes of foreign studies into the Nigerian environment as some of the insignificant factors in foreign studies were found significant in this study. Lastly, research units of organizations and indeed scholars are invited to take interest in furthering research in this area and integrate additional variables into the regression model as the goodness of fit of the study is adjudged weak.

Keywords: Brand, Brand preference (Bp), Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Environmental Factors (EF), Customer Relations (CR).

INTRODUCTION

Marketing as we know it today would have been hollow without the branding of products. In short, its evolution and development have been both anaemic and stunted. A brand is an identity with which a product is known, distinguished and set aside from any other product (Kotler, 2013). Branding is a process that carries with it unique product attributes, signatures, slogans and insignia etc., which confers value, prestige and worth on a particular product or product category.

An emerging pattern in brand management is the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) to create relationships between a company and its brand (image) on the one hand and the public (target market) it is committed to serving on the other. Therefore, it is argued, brand management and CRM may be like Siamese twins that move in the same direction to warrant product and organizational success.

Brand preference is the effect a consumer has on a product image, which permits him/her to adopt brand A instead of brand B. The place of CRM in accentuating this perceptual tendency is apt. Czellar and Palazzo (2004) tried to explore perception as its impact on brand preference in their exploratory study. They found that perceived corporate values and value importance positively affect brand preference and that its effect is motivated by individual differences which they defined in terms of self-monitoring and materialism.

As brands, signatures and insignia are owned by corporate organizations; their perceptions are a matter of generic concern not only to Customer Relations managers but also to stakeholders. A corporate brand tries to establish a coherent perception of the company for its different stakeholders and reflects a good corporate reputation in the eyes of the general public. (D'Maria and Micelli 2007; Bradley, 2003) all make attestations to this conception.

Again, value-driven brands help to express or sometimes define customers' personal moral preferences; in addition, they can transport specific aspects of consumer personalities. Also, values build the evaluative framework that helps to reconstruct, maintain and express a role-transcending and cross-situational including consistent identity (Hilton, 2003; Taylor 1989). CR manager in building brand relationships can exploit the combinations of values, personal, moral preferences and personality characteristics as basic ingredients in creating a successful branding programme.

Berry (2000) in an earlier investigation had suggested factors of rationality and economy as capable of sparking feelings of closeness; affection and trust, which are key ingredients or building blocks in establishing a brand relationship. Hence, we may theorize that CRM can help in moulding the tendency to like or prefer a brand.

In a working paper Kelly, Goldsmith and Dhar (2008) wanted to ascertain the influence of consumers' mindset on brand extension, the research shows many consumers still prefer the store brands.

However, much as many studies have revealed these outcomes and dimensions of knowledge in branding, brand preference, brand trust, customer morale and personality attributes in building brand loyalty, there is a dearth of

research effort on the influence of CRM and environmental factors on brand preferences (Bp) in the purchase of electronic brands in South-South Nigeria. This is the provocateur of this study.

Objectives of the study: In light of the above statements, the general purpose of this study is to determine the impact CRM and the External environment can exert on a customer to make him/her have a preference for a specific brand of electronic product. Specifically, the study is focused to:

1. To determine the nature of the relationship between CRM and brand preference (Bp)
2. To Ascertain the relationship between the external environment and brand preference
3. To find out if customer attraction, conversion, retention, relationship management, privacy, family, peer group, economic, competition, technology, and indeed culture can predict brand preference.

Study Questions: In the light of the above objectives, the following research questions become imperative to drive this study.

1. What is the nature of the relationship existing between CRM and Brand preference?
2. What association exists between the external environment and brand preference?
3. Can factors of customer attraction, conversion, retention, relationship management, privacy, family, peer group, technology, economic, competition, and culture influence customer brand preference?

Study Hypotheses

Hypotheses One: There is no relationship between CRM and brand preference

Hypothesis Two: There is no relationship between environmental factors and the preferences customers have for certain electronic brands

Hypothesis Three: The factors of customer attraction, conversion, retention, relationship management, privacy, family, peer group, technology, economy, competition and culture do not influence customer brand preference.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Conceptual Exposition

Customer relationship management has gained increased acceptance in real industrial settings. This is because managing the customer for a lifetime is regarded as better than engaging in a one-off transaction relationship and thence continues to hunt for customers all over again and continuously. The cost incurred in this continuous exercise of customer "hit-and-run" can be humongous over time. Sepulcri (2003) says CRM is about understanding the preferences of customers and using that information to maximize the probability of a sale or improve the level of service. This conception means CRM has an association with the product or brand preferences of customers as it can deliver better services and satisfaction to target markets.

Again, Lau (2007) conceives it as a platform for understanding and effectively identify, foster and retain loyal, profitable customers for the benefit of the firm. This presupposes that CRM is about building brand loyal customers that will add value to the firm's array of products and brands. Hence, in his reasoning, CRM embraces the three crucial dimensions of customer interfaces:

1. Mutual commitment to fulfil obligations of the relationship. The organization should provide quality services or brands.
2. In return, the customer should deliver value that is profitable to the organization.
3. Customers should trust in the organization's ability and capability to deliver what they promised and continuously.

Goldberg (Undated) provides a unifying summation of the concept and ramifications of CRM. For him, CRM integrates people, processes, and technology to maximize the relationship with all customers. It is a comprehensive approach that provides seamless coordination between all customer-facing functions. When firms go the length of doing all of these and more, it means the firm is desirous of etching its brand image cognitively in the thought process and buying actions of the customer.

The concept of the marketing environment has received much attention from scholars of marketing (Ekakitie, 2015; Agbonifoh 2008; Achumba, 2001). The economic environment as adduced by Iyoha and Ekanem (2002) imposes constraints and opportunities on any business enterprise. It influences the level of competitiveness and choice-making on aggregates of products and services offered in any economy. Ekakitie (2010) sees the external marketing environment as a propeller of need states and such need states can have telling influences on product brands and the choices customers make. The external environment thus buffets the customer in many ways.

Factors inherent in the marketing environment such as family, peer group, culture, budgets, and competitions, legal and other sociopolitical underpinnings all combine to impose influences on the choice of brands customers make. Thus, along the 4Ps of marketing dynamics, the external environment can impose a review of policies on prices firms charge for their brand, ditto how a brand should be promoted to meet market acceptance, its distribution networks and indeed its targeting and repositioning strategies (Jobber, 2008; Kotler and Keller 2008). In the succeeding paragraphs, the study illustrates the framework that drives the survey administration.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Source: Researcher's Model 2020

The figure above represents the conceptualized model of this study. Conceptually, many authors have suggested what they think a CRM programme should consist of. Authors like Kotler and Keller (2008) have pinpointed media efforts to attract customers as a foremost component. They also aver that customer retention is another key ingredient of a CRM programme. Before now, Buttle (1996), Fornell (1992), Hillier (1999); and Rust, Zahorik and Keiningham (1996) have cited customer retention, corporate profit, and increased market share as driving forces behind effective CRM. But McKinsey & Co. (1999) and Winner (2001) both agree that the components of an effective CRM programme include customer attraction, retention and conversion, measurement and privacy issues. The following discusses pertains to variables underpinning the model.

C.R.M. DOMAIN FACTORS

Customer Attraction

According to Kotler (2006) customer acquisition required substantial skills in lead generation, lead qualification, and account conversion. In his opinion, to generate leads means the development of advertisements and placing them on media (televisions, radio, magazines etc) to reach new prospects; it also includes sending direct mails, phone calls, engaging in trade shows and sales promotion campaigns, from these activities, a list of likely customers (prospects) can be generated. This list can be segmented or categorized into three (3) sets of "hot prospects", "warm prospects" and "cool prospects".

The first step in entrenching a viable CRM programme is the task of customer attraction. Because customers are the reasons for the business, the entrepreneur must evolve all strategies to identify and secure the people (customer) that will buy his product/service offerings. In this sense, promotional

programmes and campaigns are necessary steps to inform, educate and sensitize the identified market. Brands when properly positioned tend to impart preferences along with a range of choices.

Customer Conversion

Customers have several directions to which they lean. Many customers have reasons for leaning towards a particular direction to satisfy their needs/wants. Once they have had their attention and interest sufficiently aroused (AIDA), (Jobber, 2004) the next step is to convert them. Customer conversion involves a complex of psychological and objective variables which add impetus to their planned behaviour. Very often it takes a lot of tact to convert an adversary's client (your competitor) to become your client. Many times you have to investigate need areas your competitor is not filling or neglected and you have to deploy strategies to cause their customers to switch over to your company and product by filling the need vacuum you have spotted.

Customer Retention

Customer retention is a crucial component of the CRM programme. Its existential philosophy stems from the belief that it is better to keep a "won" customer than allow him to "leave" due to lack of customer care and value delivery. Researchers such as Reichheld and Sassar (1990) have asserted that a 5% improvement in customer retention can cause an increase in profitability of between 24% and 85% (in terms of net present value) depending on the industry.

It is not out of place that these figures might lack empiricism or even specificity due to faulty cross-sectional analysis. As Carrol and Reichheld (1992) have argued, it is generally true that increased profitability results from customer retention. In this regard, Buchanan and Giles (1990) argue that the profitability which results from customer retention is a direct fallout of several factors as cost of acquisition, account maintenance cost, long-term customers tending to be less inclined to switching, long-term customers are like partners that deploy Word-of-Mouth (WOM) to make first-time or new customers stay.

Customer Maintenance

Customer maintenance is another crucial component of the CRM programme. The philosophy is that a won customer is an asset and a promoter of the business. Loudon and Loudon (2008) avers that maintaining a customer is a needful administrative exercise that should involve correctly ascertaining the need profile of the customer periodically and measuring the direction of current and future preferences. This will enable the customer and firm to develop a sense of mutual commitment to the relationship. After attracting them, there's the need to integrate them into the "brand family" such that as they go back home they are "delighted and happy" enough to come back (Kotler and Keller, 2008). The second purchase experience should provide the "thrill" which secures them.

Privacy issues

As the CRM system depends on specific customer issues on privacy come under consideration. Thus each customer has the right to the confidentiality of his profile. This helps build a relationship and enhances factual information sharing. As Winner (2001) puts it on particularly with the popularity of the internet many consumers and advocacy groups are concerned about the amount of personal information that is contained in the database and how it is being used.

A study by Forrester Research found a continuum of privacy concerns.

1. Simple irritation- this came mainly from unwanted mails
 2. Feeling of violation or "How do they know that about me"
 3. Fear of harm. This could come from browsing X-rated sites book travel that a consumer does not want others to know about, and so on.
 4. Nightmarish visions- the IRS," Big brother" and other thought
- These privacy concerns along with the personalization of services can have effects on the level and direction of brand choices customers and prospects make on brands of electronics.

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

The external environment consists of factors of family, peer group, technology, competitiveness, economic, and socio-cultural factors. This environment is touted to affect brand preference. The following are key:

Family: The family is regarded by sociologist as the smallest unit of society. Several definitions have been preferred over the years to teach the concept. Literarily speaking, the family consists of a household (i.e. a socio-economic unit) that live together having a father, mother and children. Several variants of the family have also been exhaustively taught in books of sociology and socio-psychology. Within the context of the family, purchase duties and choices of brands to procure for consumption fall largely on the mother i.e. for consumable goods. For goods of instrumental and capital nature, the father is the decision-maker on what brands to buy. Purchase behaviour and brand choice are also influenced by the stages in the family life cycle. The family life cycle imposes constraints on product choice and brand selection (Achumba 2000; Kotler and Keller, 2008).

Peer Group: A foremost influencer of individual and group behaviour is the peer group. A peer group consists of individuals, and even organized units that share a common experience through close knitting. Individuals and persons may have passed through some form of social institutions like educational institutions, religious institutions etc., and have acquired training in defined areas for knowledge or skill. Peer group members tend to influence one another and in extreme cases, there is a manifestation of bandwagon behaviour. Certain norms are held strongly – in some cases, the norms assume the dimension of rules. In behavioural theory, peer group members manifest the herd behaviour. Here the group leaders set the rules and dictate the direction and all other members

follow. This implies that such issues of marketing import as individual freedom to exercise discretion on specific brands that will discharge needs and wants states are lost and the evaluative and reasoning process including privacy needs of the customer are wished away as the group ideology prevails.

Technology: Technology is considered as one of the world's fastest agents of transformation that is a consequence of change and innovation (Ekakitie, 2009). Technology is a product of innovation and inventions which prevail at a time and have an impact on the production of goods and services. According to Hyson and Bolce, (1983) technology provides a wide range of challenges and concerns for today's business managers. Without modern technology, enterprises and industries lose their competitive edge. One strong and perhaps powerful impact of technology lies in its capacity to achieve economies of scale through mass production, making machines more efficient to warrant the lower cost and lower price thereby making consumer's purchase more. A strong variant of technology of our times is the information and communication technology ICT. The information age according to Dholakia and Dholakia (1995) makes technology an instantaneous culture of change and social marketing, this no doubt impart brand presentence and choice

Competition: This connotes rivalry among firms – Porter (1981) identified these forces to include suppliers (and their bargaining powers), buyers (and their bargaining powers), potential entrants (threat of entrants), and substitute firms (threats of substitutes products and services. Competitiveness according to Ekakiitie (2009) throws up critical issues of economies of scale, product differentiation, capital requirements, and switching costs. Other issues include how to cope with challenges and improvements in channel efficiency and cost disadvantages. In consumer behaviour, competitiveness and rivalry offer the consumer leverage to make product choices through the arrays of brands offerings, packaging and promotional activities geared to stimulate demand. Promotion and marketing communications through media wars help the uninformed customer make better decisions on the brand choices available.

Economic factors: The economic environment exerts an influence on the individual and household consumption of products and services. Fiscal policies of government point the direction of public spending; it determines sectoral allocation, and such issues as taxation and borrowing (Familoni, 2001; Iyoha and Ekanem 2006). More tax on individual or organizations can reduce disposable income and savings. Generally, the economic environment has a compelling effect on consumer behaviour and brand choice-making within the context of prevailing economic circumstances which affect his spending, including scarcity and choice indices.

Socio-Cultural factors: By culture we mean simply the way people and individuals do things, conduct their affairs and generally the pattern of living. For Stoner, et al (2004) culture represent a set of important understanding, such as norms, attitudes, values and beliefs shared by members of a group or society. Kreitner's (2004) conception has a rule orientation. For him, culture is a

framework that guides day to day behaviour and decision making which is pervasive, shared and transmitted. Thus according to Achumba's (2000) categorization, culture has some variances: cognitive component, material culture, normative component. He also posits that it has some functional responsibilities to society and its people in that it fulfills a socialization function in addition to it being learnable, prescriptive and adaptive.

REVIEW OF MODELS

Several models have been postulated by behaviourists to explain the customer reasoning processes on the way to making choices on preferred brands. Engel, Blackwell and Miniard (1986) identified three decision process strategies exhibited by customers. They include the Extended Problem Solving (EPS) that lies at one polar extreme - it imposes demands on the consumer in terms of time and energy, and aligns itself most with high involvement products which are tied to customer brand preferences and prestige.

The Routine Problem Solving (RPS) at the other end of the continuum exhibits pervasive human characteristics that shift from EPS to RPS in a fluctuating manner. Lastly, the Limited Problem Solving (LPS) has its locus between the two poles of the Decision Process Strategies (DPS) continuum. It exhibits two characteristics: (1) that of EPS which admits the use of information and active reasoning about a brand choice with a lesser degree of search and evaluation (2) it is not routinized, even though this type of decision has the character of minimized or reduced mental behaviour. It is worthy to mention that John Dewey's (1910) conceptualization of decision process behaviour created the foundation for the understanding of EPS.

Another foremost model of brand preferences is the Personal Influence Model (PIM). This model has communication as its fundamental driver. This states that the alternative brand which has the highest influences on the positive and negative communication continuum will be the one selected. The model is expressed mathematically as $\sum i = f(PCi)$, $\sum i = \text{Maximum}$.

Where the dependent variable ($\sum i$) is the evaluation of brands, and products and the independent variable (PCi), the personal communications received about the brand. The framework below tries to explain its very essence.

From this model, one can conclude that effective advertising and the communication of brand types and relevant information to the right market at the right time would build a cognitive knowledge about the choices available for evaluation and thus provide the stimulus that will provoke a brand response and brand preference in the task of a purchase decision making.

The Stochastic Model

Source: Engel, James, Blackwell, Roger and Miniard, Paul (1986) *Consumer Behaviour* 5th edition New York, NY 10017, The Dryden Press, pp 24 The Stochastic Model is a probability model which operates on the principles that a consumer's previous purchase and particularly the most recent (purchase) do influence his preferences in subsequent purchases.

Two components have been attributed to the model:

- ⇒ a model that identifies individual behaviour and
- ⇒ a method of aggregating the individual models

According to Achumba (1996), the stochastic model is of the essence in determining individual consumer's brand loyalty or choice – thus purchase actions of the consumer at the marketplace is seen as fallouts of the probabilistic process. Therefore, the probabilistic model is grounded on two broad philosophies that: (1) several factors determine the outcome of behaviour and some of them are not scientifically measurable or explicitly so – these include: attitude, personality, income etc., as well as other varieties of market, generated information: advertising, price, promotional campaigns etc. (2) that it is not at all times that consumer market can be interpreted in stochastic dimension but also the actual consumer behaviour – hence random choice making (a brain attribute) in brand preference can be observed and do occur.

Again, the brand loyalty model developed by Morrison lends much credence to brand preference and adoption. The model holds that the brand choice probabilities which are influenced by the most recent purchase can be mathematically expressed: $A(A + 1/At) = P$. According to Morrison, A is the consumer-preferred brand and $P(A + 1)$ represents the chances that the consumer will buy brand A at purchase occasion + 1

For a brand to be the preferred brand the customer must have perceived it to fit into his requirement as capable of discharging his needs. Perception influences attitude and attitude is manifested in behaviour i.e. buying behaviour.

Rajeki (1989), a socio-psychologists conceptualized attitude to follow the ABC model of attitudes in his adoption of the suggestion that attitude has three components: for him, the affect component encompasses our positive or negative emotions about something – how we feel about it etc. The behavioural component consists of a predisposition or intention to act in a particular manner

that is reflective or relevant to our attitude. Conclusively, the cognitive component refers to the beliefs and thoughts we hold about objects of our attitude. It is worthy to note that this link between attitude and behaviour is not permanent for all time. No research work has supported its permanence and it is pertinent to state concisely that perception brings about attitude in a large range of ramifications. Thus people like or dislike a product (attitude) based on how they perceive the product.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The survey research method was adopted in this investigation. Instruments of data capture included the questionnaire only. The questionnaire forms were administered randomly to the sample population. The target population consisted of buyers of popular brands of electronics across five (5) cities of the South-South of Nigeria. These cities are Asaba, Benin City, Port Harcourt, Yenegoa and Calabar. The sampling techniques used to drive the study is accidental i.e. questionnaires are administered to individuals and small retailers who come to buy electronic brands from major dealers across these five cities. Five brands were selected – these include LG, Samsung, Sony, Panasonic, and Toshiba.

Sample Size: The general sample populations for this investigation are individual household buyers and small dealers of electronic products whose brands have been mentioned. These make purchases from the major dealers in each city or town. In Benin City, 20 dealers were identified. In Asaba, 12 major dealers were identified, in Yenagoa, 10 were identified. In the cities of Port Harcourt and Calabar 28 and 22 were identified respectively. Out of these Niger Delta cities, questionnaires were given to individual buyers and small-batch buyers. Because it is difficult to delineate the purchases pattern in terms of how many buyers will purchase at any given time or period and the regularity of small-batch buyers, accidental methods were adopted. This is to eliminate bias (Asika 2000). A time frame of three (3) weeks was given to allow each major dealer to give and retrieve questionnaires from individual and small batch buyers.

The following numbers of customers were captured:

Major dealers	No.	Deposited	No. of buyers
Asaba	12	120	90
Benin City	20	235	180
Yenagoa	10	123	66
Port Harcourt	28	312	230
Calabar	22	320	212
	=====		=====
TOTAL	92	1,110	778

Of 1,110 questionnaire distributed to 92 dealers across the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, a total number of 778 questionnaires were successfully retrieved from responding individuals. This gives a response rate of 70%. Curran and Blackburn (2001) in their study say a good sample and standard response in any study should achieve a 60% response rate. This study has surpassed this quality.

Validity was censured by a pilot study using only Asaba and Benin City. Dichotomous questions were used to ascertain various predictor factors. By way of data presentation and analysis, the researcher used simple tables and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences SPSS, to run a multiple regression programme on the dependent variable. Two sets of independent variables are used, first singly on the dependent variable and in turn, then collectively to ascertain which factor(s) will be significant predictors or otherwise

Dependent Variables

Bp = Brand Preference, consist of the following variables:

Bp = f(Bap, Baf, Bc, Bs, Bt)

Ba = Brand Appeal – i.e. extent a brand appeals to a customer

Baf = Brand Affect – the extent of personal affection/feeling or personal attachment to the brand

Bc = Brand Cognition – the extent of customer knowledge/awareness of the brand

Bs = Brand Sensitivity – the extent of a customer's sensitivity and consciousness (or alertness) for the brand and

Bt = Brand Trust – the extent to which customer has implicit confidence in the brand.

Independent Variables

CRM = f (Ca, Cc, Cr, Rm, Pv)

Where:

Ca = Customer attraction, Cc = Customer conversion, Cr = Customer retention, Rm = Relationship management, Mt = Measurement, and Pv = Privacy.

In respect of hypothesis three (3) the independent variables are expressed thus:

Ext Env = f (Fm, Pg, Cmp, Ec, Tch., Clt)

Where:

Fm = Family of origin, Pg = Peer group pressure, Cmp = Competiveness, Ecn = Economic, Tc = Technology, Ctl = Culture

Data Presentation and Analyses

The test statistics deployed for this investigation is the Regression model. This model is chosen because it enabled the ascertainment of the following:

- The impact of CRM components on brand preference (Bp) - this helped to extrapolate and bring out the variables that make the most impact, the same is true for environmental factors on Bp.
- It will assist in ascertaining the nature of the relationship CRM and the External Environment has with Brand preference (Dp).

Statistically, the test is made at a 0.05% level of significance.

Now the multiple regression model on both cases run thus:

$\ln (P_i / 1 - P_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1. Ca + \beta_2. Cc + \beta_3. Cr + \beta_4. Rm + \beta_5. Pv + \beta_6. Fm + \beta_7. Pg + \beta_8. Tc + \beta_9. Cmp + \beta_{10}. Ec + \beta_{11}. Cl + \epsilon_1$

Data Presentation and Analyses

The following are the outcome of the respondent's opinion of the questionnaire administered in the study.

Research question one enquired into the nature of the relationship between CRM and brand preference. A sample of 778 respondents suggests a good and positive relationship. Factors of customer attraction, retention, relationship management and privacy post a positive correlation coefficient with the dependent variable. Only the factor of customer conversion posted a negative relationship as can be revealed in Table 1 below. This implies that customer conversion as a factor is an inhibitor. Thus, the null hypothesis one is conveniently rejected. This implies that CRM domain factors and indeed CRM as a customer-centric strategy is key to influencing customer preferences for specific brands of electronic products for household use in Nigeria.

Table 1
ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	5	122.548	24.5096	15.66494369	1.05E-14
Residual	773	1209.447	1.564614		
Total	778	1331.995			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	3.440133	0.12763	26.95399	2.458E-113
CA	0.138542	0.095521	1.450383	0.14735742
CC	-0.67967	0.103742	-6.55157	1.03888E-10
CR	0.310958	0.11238	2.767024	0.005792225
RM	0.382618	0.111424	3.433898	0.000626661
PR	0.170615	0.110261	1.547383	0.122180283

Source: Field questionnaire, September 2020

Table 2 below pertains to research question two, and its accompanying hypothesis. The key question was to determine if there is a relationship between the external environmental factors and the tendency for customer brand preference. Table 2 reveals that of the 6 factors in that domain, 5 have a positive relationship with brand preference tendencies in the 778 respondents sampled. Thus the factors of family, peer group, technology, competition and even culture have positive coefficients with the dependent variable. Only the factor of economic posted a negative relationship with the brand preference. This negative relationship signifies that money is a factor that constrains customer from buying a preferred brand of electronic products. Again, it is noteworthy from Table 2

outlay, that the factor of the peer group is not a significant predictor of brand preference; it nonetheless has a positive coefficient with the dependent variable. It can be surmised that this factor when increased in the long run may become a significant predictor and thus give the domain predictor variable a stronger footing in terms of significance. The null hypothesis, in this case, is rejected and this implies that the environment is a strong influence on brand preference. Overall, the inevitable conclusion that can be drawn herewith is that the external environment has a strong influence on the brand preference tendencies of customers to buy specific brands of electronic for household use.

Table 2
ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	6	197.315	32.88584	22.37447789	2.25E-24
Residual	772	1134.68	1.469793		
Total	778	1331.995			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	3.1029	0.108152	28.69024	8.7528E-124
FA	0.297553	0.098592	3.018018	0.002628013
PG	0.074499	0.093576	0.796136	0.426197522
EC	-0.37128	0.091423	-4.06112	5.38225E-05
TC	0.811	0.104456	7.764049	2.61397E-14
CL	0.307299	0.106318	2.890387	0.003955611
CMP	0.419064	0.095164	4.403579	1.21498E-05

Source: Field questionnaire, September 2020

The major focus of this study is the determination of factors that predict or influence brand preference for electronic products in South-South Nigeria. Eleven (11) factors were hypothesized in this regard. Table 3 below contains a summary of the regression model. It shows the diagnostic composition of the regression model. It's revealed R of 47% expresses the level of relationship between the 11 variables that make up the predictor or independent variables in the model. The R and R² adjusted reveals the proportion of the independent variable explained in the dependent variable. It also reveals its goodness of fit or power of prediction which is revealed to be 21%. Statistically, this is weak.

Concerning Table 4, regression outlay reveals certain factors of the 11 hypothesized factors to have a positive correlation coefficient with the dependent variable

Table 3

Multiple R	0.47588
R Square	0.226461
Adjusted R Square	0.215368
Standard Error	1.15903
Observations	779

Table 4

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	11	301.6455	27.42232	20.41338503	1.86E-36
Residual	767	1030.349	1.34335		
Total	778	1331.995			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	2.724754	0.139376	19.54961	2.27234E-69
CA	-0.14658	0.095701	-1.53168	0.126013614
CC*	-0.6139	0.098958	-6.2036	9.02044E-10
CR*	0.236327	0.107023	2.208189	0.027526213
RM*	0.451392	0.107848	4.185434	3.17589E-05
PR**	0.152438	0.111324	1.369313	0.171302213
FA*	0.360964	0.098045	3.681598	0.000248022
PG*	0.201733	0.09438	2.137465	0.032875815
EC*	-0.35081	0.090773	-3.86467	0.000120652
TC*	0.673398	0.104852	6.422363	2.3521E-10
CL*	0.293242	0.103669	2.828651	0.004796432
CMP*	0.433375	0.094074	4.60675	4.78808E-06

Source: Field questionnaire, September 2020

a. Predictors: (Constant), customer attraction, customer conversion, customer retention, relationship management, privacy, family, peer group, economic, technology, culture and competition context.

b. Dependent Variable: Brand preference

* Variables are significant at the 0.05 level of significance

** Test is not significant at the 0.05 level of significance

Of the 11 factors, only three factors i.e. customer attraction, customer conversion and economic have a negative correlation coefficient with the dependent variable. All other factors are positive. These include factors of customer retention, relationship management, privacy, family, peer group, technology,

culture and competition. In terms of which factor(s) are significant predictors, one can pinpoint them as follows: customer retention, relationship management, family, peer group, technology, culture and competition at a 5% level of significance. On the alternate side and In terms of significance, two factors of economic and customer conversion are revealed to be significant but are negatively correlated with the dependent variable. This study disagrees with Winner (2001), Premkumar, (2003); and Grandon, and Pearson, (2004) in terms of customer conversion. On economic capacity as an influencing factor, it confirms it as a significant factor. Kendell (2001) found economic factor as a strong influence of purchase preference. Thus there are significant means that they can become strong inhibitors in predicting brand preference behaviour of customers for household electronic products at a 5% level of significance. Again, it can be seen from the ANOVA table that the F-significance is 1.86E-36, this shows the probability of the independent variable being high predictors in the model. Indeed this assertion proved true by the number and level of significance of the predictor variables in the model. In terms of hypothesis three, therefore, the null hypothesis stands rejected given that eight (8) factors are significant in predicting customer preferences for the electronic brand in the Niger Delta.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, it can be seen that certain factors do predict customer preference for brands of electronic products in Nigeria. While eight such factors as enunciated in the above findings are significant predictors, three are significant in terms of the power of inhibition and are therefore regarded as constraining factors in the model. Two factors (privacy and customer attraction) are not significant influencers. In respect of the type of relationship that exists between CRM and external factors in the environment vis-a-vis the dependent variable, it was revealed to be a positive one and strong in correlational effects.

RECOMMENDATION

The result of this study has very interesting outcomes. It shows that scholars should be careful in making generalized statements on factors touted or recommended in studies in a foreign environment to be significant influencers of brand preference. This study revealed customer conversion and economic as constraining factors in South Sough Nigeria. Brand managers in this part of Nigeria may have to pay special attention to them in their customer-centric programmes. Again, because economic factor still poses a strong determinant of brands preferences and purchase, brand managers should provide assortment, especially in smaller sizes to enable customers with weak purchasing power to buy. Finally, R&D units of sales outlets and indeed researchers should search for other factors to include in the range of factors that influence brand preference. This is a result of the revealed weakness of the model in this study.

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